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An Orthodontic Study of the Relation between Anterior Crossbite and Temporomandibular Disorders

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Abstract

Background: Anterior crossbite is an abnormal labiolingual relationship between one or more maxillary and mandibular anterior incisor teeth. This study was conducted to assess the prevalence of the anterior crossbite of Iraqi student sample in randomly selected primary schools in Baghdad and assess its effect on temporomandibular joint. The investigation was carried out on males and females at age range between 7-11 years.

Materials and methods: The number of examined students was 6758 (3385 female, 3373 male). The assessment procedure was done by direct examination on patient's mouth using vernier and the examination of temporomandibular joint was done according to World Health Organization (1997).

Result .The relative frequency of anterior crossbite was 1.1%. There was statistically significant difference in the relative frequency of TMD in cases with anterior crossbite.

Key words: anterior crossbite, TMDs

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Introduction

Anterior crossbite is one of the commonest malocclusion to be presented to general dental practitioner in growing children¹. It is defined as an abnormal labiolingual relationship between one or more maxillary and mandibular anterior incisor^{2,19}, as shown in fig1. Clinically, it is expressed as a "reversed overjet" in which one or more maxillary incisor teeth are positioned lingually to mandibular incisor teeth when the patient closed his mouth into centric occlusion, it could be skeletal, functional or dental^{2,4,6,7,19,5}. Anterior crossbite may consider as a traumatic occlusion¹⁰ which may lead to an abnormal path of closure and later on to a temporomandibular disorders¹⁶ (Fig 2). TMDs include variety of different disorders involving the TMJ and the muscle of mastication separately or together^{11,18}. It is found in a longitudinal study on children that crossbite are more likely associated with development of TMDs than other types of malocclusion¹⁴. Anterior crossbite cause excessive tension on TMJ causing marked deviations of the mandible on opening and closing. The condyle may be positioned downward and forward and may lead to its anterior resorption. In this study we try to assess the prevalence of anterior crossbite in Iraqi

students aged between 7-11 years in primary schools in Baghdad and its effect on TMJ

Materials and Methods

The sample had been selected from 20 primary schools in Baghdad city (Karekh and Rusapha), which was randomly selected during the period between October 2004 to the end of December 2004. The age range of the subjects was comprised of between 7-11 years. The samples was 6758 students ;3373 female and 3385 male) Table (1)

The sample was selected with the following criteria:

1. Upper and lower first molars are present.
2. Upper and lower centrals are present and fully erupted.
3. No previous orthodontic treatment and facial asymmetry

Instruments and supplies:

Plane mouth mirrors, millimeter graded vernier and Stethoscope.

Examination area

All students were examined to detect the subjects who have anterior crossbite Then, each one of them with anterior crossbite was age- and sex- matched with a control subject entering the same criteria mentioned above, except the presence of anterior crossbite, and randomly selected among other students. Natural light was utilized with the aid of portable light. The examination was done through the following sequential steps:-

1. Each student was comfortably seated in a chair with high backrest with his/her head supported in an upright position²²
2. Each subject was asked to swallow and then to close into maximum intercuspation to obtain a centric occlusion.²¹

Table (1): The percentage of the number of examined students in relation to the number of students present in Baghdad primary schools.

Age	Female		%	Male		%
	No. of students	No. of examined		No. of students	No. of examined	
7-11 years	19576	3385	1.7	22658	3373	1.4
	5			2		

TMJ assessment^{22,17}

A-Symptoms: The following codes and criteria were used:

0=No symptoms.

1=Occurrence of clicking, pain or difficulties in opening or closing the jaw once or more per week.

9= not recorded.

B- Signs: The following codes and criteria were used:

0=No signs.

1=Occurrence of clicking, tenderness (on palpitation) or reduced jaw mobility (Opening<30mm).

TMJ sounds:

This was assessed with the use of the stethoscope on the lateral aspect of each joint in front of the tragus^{16,13}, while the subject was asked to open and close his mouth.

Maximal opening of the mouth

It can be determined by measuring maximum jaw opening in the incisor region adding the amount of overbite¹¹.The inter incisal distance was measured by a vernier graded in millimeter¹⁶.One end of the vernier was placed against the incisal edge of one of the lower incisor and the vertical distant to the incisal edge of the opposing upper incisor while the subject held his \her mouth as wide as possible was measured to the nearest half of a millimeter.

#Tenderness

Tenderness was examined by palpitation of the anterior temporalis and\or masseter muscle on one or both sides. The tenderness was evaluated by unilateral palpitation with soft and firm pressure of two fingers were applied to the designated muscles for 1or 2 seconds during palpitation the patient is asked whether the pressure hurts or just uncomfortable^{17,18}. The patient's response is placed in one or four categories¹⁵:

0=no pain and response.

I=palpitation is uncomfortable.

II=definite discomfort and pain.

III=shows evasive action.

C-Deviation on maximal mouth opening: It was measured by drawing a vertical line with an indelible pencil on the midline from the upper incisors down to

the opposing lower incisor. Then the patient was asked to open his \her mouth, any horizontal deviation of 2mm or more upon closing and opening was recorded. The direction of the shifting was also recorded¹⁶

Anterior displacement:

Any patient with a mild reverse overjet and positive overbite should be examined for anterior displacement⁶. The patient was in centric occlusion and his occlusal plane was horizontal, a vertical line was drawn with an indelible pencil on the midline from the upper incisors down to the opposing lower incisor¹⁶ First the student was asked to close in centric relation.The incisors meet edge to edge relation but the posterior teeth are out of occlusion. In order to obtain a position of maximum occlusion, the mandible was displaced anteriorly, so there is over closure of the mandible in this case⁶.

Result

Table (2) showed that the total number of examined students, and the number of control groups, in addition to the number of students with anterior crossbite, (unilateral and bilateral).

Table (2): The total number of examined students, number of control groups, and number of students with anterior crossbite.

	Male	Female	Total
Examined	3373	3385	6758
Control	100	100	200
Unilateral crossbite	34	27	61
Bilateral crossbite	6	4	10

Frequency of anterior crossbite

A- Age and gender

The table 3 showed that there was no statistically significant difference in prevalence rate of anterior crossbite

between male and female in each age group. But there was a statistically significant difference in prevalence rate of anterior crossbite between age groups.

Table (3) The relative frequency (prevalence rate) of identified anterior cross-bite by age, and gender.

Age in years	Male			Female			Z	P
	Examined	Anterior Cross-bite	%	Examined	Anterior Cross-bite	%		
	No	No	%	No	No	%		
7	670	8	1.2	674	6	0.9	0.28	0.78 ^[NS]
8	668	10	1.5	673	13	1.9	0.4	0.69 ^[NS]
9	713	13	1.8	713	4	0.6	1.95	0.05
10	754	9	1.2	758	4	0.5	1.12	0.26 ^[NS]
11	568	4	0.7	567	0	0.0	0.41	0.13 ^[NS]
Total	3373	44	1.3	3385	27	0.8	1.93	0.05

Figure (3): Prevalence rate of anterior crossbite

Figure (4): Prevalence rate of anterior crossbite between male and female.

B- Tooth

Table (4) showed that the majority of subjects have one tooth affected with anterior crossbite

Table (4): Frequency distribution of cases with anterior cross-bite by number of affected teeth.

Number of tooth presenting with anterior cross bite	N	%
1	61	85.9
2	9	12.7
4	1	1.4
Total	71	100

Table (5) showed that the upper left central incisor is the most affected tooth with anterior crossbite (unilateral and

bilateral), while the upper right lateral incisor is the less one affected.

Table (5): The relative frequency of each type of upper incisor manifesting the anterior cross bite unilateral and bilateral cases

Teeth affected by anterior cross-bite	unilateral anterior cross-bite (n=61)		Bilateral anterior cross-bite (n=10)		Total anterior cross bite (n=71)	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Upper left central incisor	36	59	8	80	44	62
Upper right central incisor	11	18	8	80	19	26.8
Upper left lateral incisor	8	13.1	3	30	11	15.5
Upper right lateral incisor	6	9.8	3	30	9	12.7

Figure (5): Relative frequency of a tooth affected by anterior crossbite

Temporomandibular joint examinations

A-Temporomandibular joint symptoms

Table (6) showed that there was statistically significant difference in the relative frequency of temporomandibular joint symptoms between control subjects and subjects with anterior crossbite

Table (7) showed that there was no statistically significant difference in the relative frequency' tenderness of masseter and temporalis between unilateral and bilateral anterior crossbite cases.

Table (6): Case-control difference in relative frequency of TMJ symptoms

TMJ-symptoms	Controls (n=200)		Cases - Anterior x-bite (n=71)		χ^2	df	P
	N	%	N	%			
	0	(0)	4	(5.6)			

Table(7): The relative frequency difference of TMJ symptoms between unilateral and bilateral anterior crossbite cases

Positive findings	Unilateral anterior x-bite		Bilateral anterior x-bite		χ^2	df	P
	N	%	N	%			
TMJ-Symptoms	2	3.3	2	20	**	**	0.09 ^[NS]

B-Temporomandibular joint signs

Table (8) showed that there was a statistically significant difference in the relative frequency of TMJ signs between the control group and cases with anterior crossbite.

Table (8): Case-control difference in relative frequency of TMJ signs

Positive findings	Controls (n=200)		Cases - Anterior crossbite (n=71)		χ^2	df	P
	N	%	N	%			
TMJ-Click	11	5.5	21	29.6	29.2	1	<0.001
Tenderness-Masseter muscle	4	2	6	8.5	**	**	
Tenderness-Temporalis	4	2	5	7	**	**	

Table(9): showed that the clicking and the tenderness of temporalis and masseter muscle showed no statistically significant difference in the relative frequency between subjects with anterior unilateral crossbite and subjects with bilateral anterior crossbite.

Table(9): The difference between unilateral and bilateral anterior cross-bite- in relative frequency of muscle tenderness and clicking

Positive findings	Unilateral anterior cross-bite (n=61)		Bilateral anterior crossbite (n=10)		χ^2	df	P
	N	%	N	%			
TMJ-Click	16	26.2	5	50	**	**	0.15 ^[NS]
tenderness-Masseter muscle	4	6.6	2	20	**	**	0.2 ^[NS]
Tenderness-Temporalis muscle	4	6.6	1	10	**	**	0.54 ^[NS]

The table (10) showed that there are agreements between clicking and the side of crossbite tooth about 81.8%

Table (10): Relation between the side of crossbite and the side of clicking

side of anterior cross bite tooth	TMJ-clicking				
	Negative	Right	Left	Both sides	Total
Right	12	2	0	3	17
Left	33	2	7	2	44
Total	45	4	7	5	61

Agreement = $2 + 7 / 11 = 81.8\%$

Table (11) showed that the mean mouth opening was significantly lower in subjects with anterior crossbite (unilateral and

bilateral cases) which is equal to 37mm-compared with control subjects which is equal to 43.6mm.

Table (11): Case-control difference in the mean mouth opening.(in mm)

	Control s (n=200)	Cases (Anterior crossbite) (n=71)	t	df	P
Mouth opening (mm)			11.3	269	<0.001
Range	(33-54)	(30-46)			
Mean	43.6	37			
SD	4.26	4.07			
SE	0.301	0.483			

Table (12) showed that the mean mouth opening was the same in

subjects with anterior crossbite (unilateral and bilateral cases)

Table (12): The difference between Cases with unilateral and those with bilateral anterior crossbite in mean mouth opening. (in mm)

	Unilateral anterior crossbite	Bilateral anterior crossbite	t	df	P
Mouth opening (mm)			0.035	69	0.97 ^[NS]
Range	(30-46)	(30-43)			
Mean	37	37			
SD	3.95	4.99			
SE	0.506	1.578			

Anterior displacement:

Table (13) showed that there was a statistically significant difference in the relative frequency of anterior

displacements between control subjects and subjects with anterior crossbite.

Table (13): Case-control difference in relative frequency of anterior displacement.

	Controls (n=200)		Cases (Anterior cross-bite) (n=71)				
Positive findings	N	%	N	%	χ^2	df	P
Anterior displacement	21	10.5	19	26.8	11.0	1	0.001

** Fisher's exact significance

(Table 14) showed that there was no statistically significant difference in the relative frequency

of anterior displacements between subjects with unilateral and bilateral anterior crossbite

Table (14): The in relative frequency difference between Cases with unilateral and bilateral anterior cross-bite of anterior displacemnt.

	Unilateral anterior crossbite (n=61)		Bilateral anterior crossbite (n=10)				
Positive findings	N	%	N	%	χ^2	df	P
Anterior displacement	16	26.2	3	30	**	**	1 [NS]

** Fisher's exact significance

Discussion

Age

The prevalence rate of anterior crossbite in the samples is 1.1%. Table (3) shows that the majority of anterior crossbite cases are found between 8-9 years in female, and between 9-10 years in male as shown in fig (3,4,5). This is because of the exfoliation time in female is earlier than male. The prevalence rate of frequency will decrease with growing age because the incisors erupt earlier than other permanent teeth and they are located in

front of the mouth; therefore, they affect dental and facial appearance greatly. For the above reasons, most parents bring their children early when they have irregular incisors, seeking orthodontic treatment.¹⁰

Gender

The majority of anterior crossbite are found in males as shown in table (3), because the females here aware of their appearance more than the males

Tooth

The majority of the samples with anterior crossbite have only one affected tooth which is the left central incisors. This may be due to trauma to the tooth bud, retained deciduous teeth or delayed eruption of permanent incisor-as shown in table (4) and (5). Table (5) has shown that the lateral incisors are the least one affected differentiate between toothache, earache, and joint pain. (Table6&7) while the opposite was true in other study¹⁰. In this study, the canine has not been erupted yet. The eruption of canine later will displace the lateral palatally.

The temporomandibular disorder

A-TMJ symptoms: The prevalence of symptoms is less in children (5.6%) which agreed with other study¹³.

B-TMJ signs

1-Clicking:-

The study revealed that 29.2% of patients have clicking in comparison with control group-table (8) Patients with anterior crossbite are most likely to develop clicking at early age¹³. Clicking is seen in both unilateral and bilateral anterior crossbite-table (9)-. In children, clicking may be associated with muscle tenderness and reduced mouth opening. There is a correlation between the side of crossbite and side of clicking. Table (10)

2- Tenderness of muscles (masseter and temporalis)

Only small numbers of students have pain upon palpitation and it might be increased with growing age-Table (8) and (9)

3-Mouth opening

Restricted mouth opening is more obvious in both unilateral and bilateral anterior crossbite in comparison with the control group, (Table 11). Both unilateral and bilateral anterior crossbite have restricted mouth opening as shown in(Table 12). It might be associated with anterior displacement, muscle tenderness, and clicking

4-Anterior displacement of the mandible

Anterior crossbite is more associated with unilateral and bilateral anterior crossbite than control groups (Table12and 13). This might be related to occlusal interference which forced the patient to displace the lower teeth to get maximum interdegitation. Excessive tension can be placed on TMJ causing marked effect on opening and closing. The condyle may be positioned downward and forward and may lead to anterior resorption.

Conclusion

The prevalence rate of anterior crossbite is 1.1% The left central incisor is the most affected tooth with anterior crossbite in such group of age.The majority of anterior crossbite cases are found between 8-9 years in female, and between 9-10 years in male clicking is highly associated with crossbite side.Restricted mouth opening is more obvious in both unilateral and bilateral anterior crossbite in comparison with the control group.Anterior crossbite is highly associated with anterior displacement

References

- 1-Bodenham R, Bodenham J.: The etiology and treatment of anterior cross-bite. *The Dent. Practit.* 1969:Oct. 52-58.
- 2-Brian DL: Correction of crossbite: *Dent Clin North America*; 1978;22(4): 647-657.
- 3-Ciancaglini R, Gherlone E, Redaelli S.: The distribution of occlusal contacts in the intercuspal position and temporomandibular disorder. *J Oral Rehabil*; 2002;29:1082-1090.
- 4-Chow MH.: Treatment of anterior crossbite caused by occlusal interferences. *Quintessence International*;1979;2:57-60.
- 5-Daskologiannakis J.: Glossary of orthodontic terms. Berlin, Quintessence Publishing Co. Inc. 2000
- 6-Houston WJB.: *Orthodontic Diagnosis.* Bristol: John Write and Sons LTD: 1975
- 7-Houston WJB :*Orthodontic diagnosis.*3rd ed. Bristol; Wright PSG. 1982
- 8-Houston WJB: *Walther's Orthodontic notes.*4th edition. Bristol: John Write and Sons LTD.1983
- 9-Klinberg I, Jagger R.: *Occlusion and clinical practice*; Wright. 2004
- 10-Kinaan BK.: Treatment of lingual occlusion of upper anterior teeth. *Iraqi J of Dental Research.* 1981;2:49-59.
- 11-Keeling SD, McGorry S, Wheeler TT, King GJ.b.: Risk factors associated with Temporomandibular joint sounds in children 6 to 12 years of age. *Am J Orthod-Dentofacial.*1994;105:279-287.
- 12-Mohlin B, Derweduwen K, Pilley R, Kingdon A, Shaw WC, Kenealy P: Malocclusion and Temporomandibular Disorder: A Comparison of Adolescentswith Moderate to severe Dysfunction with those without Signs and Symptoms of Temporomandibular Disorder and Their Further Development to 30-Years of Age. *Angle Orthod*; 2003 ;74(3):319-327.
- 13-Motegi E, Miyazaki H, Ogura I, Konishi H, Sebata M: An orthodontic study of Temporomandibular joint disorders. Part 1: Epidemiological research in Japanese 6-18 years the *Angle Orthodontist*; 1992;62(4):249-256.
- 14-Nomura M, Motegi E, Isoyama Y.: Case report of lateral crossbite. Part I. Mixed dentition. *Bull Tokyo Dent Coll*; 1995;36(2): 91-97.
- 15-Okeson JP: Management of Temporomandibular joint disorder and occlusion, 4th ed. St. Louis,Mosby. 1998.
- 16-Padamsee M, Ahlin JH, Ko CM, Tsamtouris A.: Functional disorder of the stomatognathic system: part II-A review .*J pedod*; 1985;9(3):179-187
- 17-Peter S.: *Essentials of preventive and community Dentistry.* 2nd ed. Aria (medi) Publishing House. 2004
- 18-Pergamalian A, Rudy T, Zaki H, Greco C*The association between wear facets,bruxism ,and severity of facial pain in patients with Temporomandibular disorders* *Prosthet Dent*; 2003.90:194-200.
- 19-Purcell PD: The Crossbite. *J of the Michigan Dent Assoc*; 1984;66:69-73.
- 20-Rani S.: *Synopsis of orthodontics.*AITB publishers Distributors, Delhi. 1995
- 21-Rahn A, Heartwell M: *Textbook of complete dentures.*5th ed. Lippincott Walliams & Wilkins. . 1993